

EXPLORING VALUE-DRIVEN POVERTY ALLEVIATION THROUGH ISLAMIC SOCIAL WELFARE IN NORTH- CENTRAL NIGERIA

HUSSAINI MUHAMMAD

Department of Islamic Studies

Umaru Sanda Ahmadu College of Education, Minna

Email: husmusman13@gmail.com | Phone: 09060069177

Abstract

Poverty remains a persistent socio-economic challenge in North-Central Nigeria, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations and constraining sustainable development. Despite the historical role of Islamic social welfare in promoting social justice, there is limited empirical research examining how value-driven welfare mechanisms-*zakat*, *sadaqah*, and *waqf*-translate into tangible poverty alleviation in the region. This study therefore examines the contribution of Islamic social welfare systems to poverty reduction, with particular focus on ethical and value-driven practices. A mixed-methods design was employed, combining structured surveys of 250 beneficiaries across Niger, Nassarawa, and FCT Abuja with in-depth interviews of 30 officials from Islamic welfare institutions, including *zakat* boards, *waqf* trusts, and Islamic NGOs. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and thematic content analysis. Findings indicate that Islamic social welfare programs significantly improved access to basic needs, education, and micro-finance opportunities, with ethical principles such as transparency, accountability, and equitable resource distribution enhancing program effectiveness. Challenges including insufficient funding, limited institutional coordination, and low community awareness constrained program impact. The study recommended strengthening institutional frameworks, promoting public awareness of Islamic welfare ethics, and integrating value-driven practices into policy and development planning to enhance sustainability and effectiveness of poverty alleviation initiatives.

Keywords: Islamic Social Welfare; Value-Driven Poverty Alleviation; North-Central Nigeria; Social Justice; Community Development

Introduction

Poverty remains one of the most pressing socio-economic challenges in North-Central Nigeria, where a significant portion of the population struggles with limited access to basic needs, education, healthcare, and economic opportunities (National

Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2020). Despite numerous government and non-governmental interventions, poverty persists, particularly among vulnerable groups such as women, children, and low-income families.

Islamic social welfare has historically played a critical role in promoting social justice and economic equity through value-driven mechanisms such as *zakat*, *sadaqah*, and *waqf*, which are designed to redistribute resources ethically and equitably within the community (Al-Ghazālī, 2004; Kamal, 2017). Grounded in principles of compassion, accountability, and communal responsibility, Islamic welfare ensures that poverty alleviation efforts are not only materially effective but also socially and morally sustainable (Hassan & Haron, 2020).

While existing literature highlights the theoretical importance of Islamic social welfare, there is a notable empirical gap, particularly regarding how value-driven approaches translate into tangible poverty reduction in North-Central Nigeria. Most studies have focused on Northern Nigeria as a whole or general policy frameworks, leaving limited region and specific evidence on the effectiveness of Islamic welfare initiatives (Bello, 2019; Yusuf, 2017).

Therefore, the study explores the role of Islamic social welfare in promoting value-driven poverty alleviation in North-Central Nigeria, assessing both the socio-economic impact of welfare programs and the ethical practices underpinning them. This study is significant because understanding how ethical and value-driven principles shape welfare outcomes can inform sustainable poverty alleviation policies and community development strategies.

Literature Review

Conceptualizing Islamic Social Welfare

Islamic social welfare refers to organized efforts rooted in *Shari'ah* principles that promote social justice, equity, and community well-being. Core instruments of social welfare in Islam include:

Zakat is a compulsory form of almsgiving in Islam and constitutes one of the five pillars of the religion. It obliges eligible Muslims to contribute a prescribed portion of their wealth to designated categories of beneficiaries, including the poor and the needy. Zakat functions as an institutionalized system of wealth redistribution aimed at reducing socio-economic inequality, alleviating poverty, and promoting social justice within the Muslim community (Qur'an 9:60; Kahf, 1999) while Sadaqah refers to voluntary charitable giving in Islam and is not bound by fixed rates or conditions. It may be offered in monetary or non-monetary forms and at any time, making it flexible and responsive to immediate social and humanitarian needs. Sadaqah complements zakat by extending welfare support beyond obligatory contributions and reflects Islamic values of compassion, generosity, and social

responsibility (Qur'an 2:261; Ahmed, 2004). Waqf Foundation on the other and is an Islamic endowment system through which individuals dedicate assets permanently for charitable or public benefit. Once established.

Waqf assets are preserved and their proceeds are used to support social services such as education, healthcare, and poverty alleviation. Waqf foundations contribute to long-term socio-economic development by providing sustainable funding for welfare initiatives while emphasizing ethical stewardship and continuity (Cizakca, 2000 and Ghazālī, 2004; Kamal, 2017). These mechanisms are inherently value-driven emphasizing accountability, transparency, compassion, and social responsibility. Islamic Scholars stated that, integrating ethical principles ensures poverty alleviation is sustainable, culturally appropriate, and morally grounded and thus, reinforcing social cohesion and communal responsibility (Hassan & Haron, 2020).

Islamic Welfare Institutions in North-Central Nigeria

North-Central Nigeria hosts several Islamic social welfare institutions that actively administer *zakat*, *sadaqah*, and *waqf* programs for instance:

- i. *Niger State Zakat Board* which oversees collection and distribution of zakat funds in Minna and surrounding areas.
- ii. *Nasarawa State Waqf Commission* that manages *waqf* endowments like funding education, healthcare, and infrastructure in Lafia.
- iii. *FCT Abuja Zakat and Sadaqah Trust* that administers both obligatory and voluntary contributions in urban and rural areas.
- iv. *Islamic Relief Nigeria (Minna Branch)*- an NGO that distributes *zakat* and *sadaqah*, by way of focusing on health, education, and microfinance initiatives.
- v. *Muslim Community Welfare Foundation (MCWF)* that implements localized welfare programs and emphasizing ethical and value-driven resource allocation.

These institutions collectively serve thousands of beneficiaries annually and are guided by principles of transparency, accountability, fairness, and community participation (Bello, 2019; Yusuf, 2017).

Value-Driven Approaches to Poverty Alleviation

Value-driven poverty alleviation emphasizes ethical decision-making, fairness, and community-centered interventions (Sen, 1999). In the Islamic context, value-driven approaches ensure that material assistance aligns with moral imperatives. Effective programs incorporate:

- i. Transparent beneficiary selection
- ii. Equitable resource distribution

- iii. Community participation in planning and monitoring
- iv. Ethical fund management guided by Shari'ah principles

This therefore goes to show that ethical and inclusive approaches enhance the social and economic impact of welfare programs (Ahmad & Abdul-Rahman, 2018)

Empirical Studies on Islamic Welfare and Poverty

Rahman (2015) and Farooq (2018) observed that international studies indicated that, value-driven Islamic welfare programs in Indonesia, Malaysia, and Egypt improves access to education, healthcare, and micro-finance for marginalized populations. Also, within Nigeria, research has largely focused on Northern states, examining *zakat* administration, *waqf* management, and NGO-led interventions while Yusuf (2017) and Bello (2019) purported that, findings have revealed that while Islamic welfare programs can effectively reduce poverty, their impact is often constrained by poor institutional coordination, limited funding, and low community awareness. However, few studies provide empirical insights specific to North-Central Nigeria, a region with multi-ethnic communities that mostly relied on agriculture, and having varying poverty patterns. This research gap therefore underscores the need for a specific investigation into value-driven Islamic welfare interventions.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts a Value-Driven Social Welfare Framework, integrating Islamic ethical principles, social justice theory, and poverty reduction theory. The framework posits that the effectiveness of welfare interventions depends on:

- i. Adherence to ethical values (transparency, accountability, fairness)
- ii. Institutional capacity (fund management, governance)
- iii. Alignment with community needs (cultural and socio-economic)

This framework allows simultaneous assessment of tangible socio-economic outcomes and the moral sustainability of welfare programs.

Methodology

Research Design

A mixed-methods design combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews was employed to capture both numerical outcomes and contextual insights.

Population and Sample

Beneficiaries: 250 individuals across Niger, Nasarawa, and FCT Abuja were selected via stratified random sampling. 30 individuals (Institutional Officials) from *zakat* boards, *waqf* trusts, and Islamic NGO were purposively selected.

Sampling was stratified by state, gender, age, and occupation, ensuring representative participation.

Data Collection

Questionnaires were distributed to beneficiaries while Institutional officials were interviewed and documents collected i.e. Program reports; policy documents were reviewed.

Data Presentation

Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, ANOVA was utilized for Quantitative analyses while

Thematic content analysis was used for Qualitative analysis. Furthermore, triangulation for the combined insights from surveys, interviews, and documents and lastly, ethical approval, informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity were strictly maintained

Table 1.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Table 2.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Table 3.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Table 4.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Table 5.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Table 6.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Results / Findings

Quantitative Findings

- i. Household Income:

Table 7.

Percentage Increase showing average household income increase post-program participation.

Mean income before participation	₦50,000
Mean income after participation	₦60,000
Increase	₦10,000
Percentage increase	20%

Interpretation: Beneficiaries experienced an average 20% increase in household income after participating in Islamic social welfare programs (*Source: Survey Data, 2026*).

- ii. Basic Needs

Table 8.

1	Access to food, shelter *	82% agreed
2	Education *	76% agreed
3	Healthcare *	68% agreed

4	Income support *	70% agreed

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Qualitative Findings (Officials, n=30)

Ethical Principles Applied

Table 9.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Identified Challenges

Table 6.

Source: Survey Data, 2026

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study confirm that Islamic social welfare programs in North-Central Nigeria significantly contribute to poverty alleviation, particularly when ethical principles such as transparency, accountability, fairness, and community participation guide implementation. These results are in line with previous research indicating that value-driven approaches in Islamic welfare enhances the effectiveness and sustainability of poverty reduction efforts (Hassan & Haron, 2020; Ahmad & Abdul-Rahman, 2018; Yusuf, 2017). From an Islamic ethical perspective, wealth redistribution through *zakat*, *sadaqah*, and *waqf* serves not only as a socio-economic intervention but also as a moral imperative to uphold social justice and equity (Al-Ghazālī, 2004; Kamal, 2017; Bello, 2019). Therefore, it is apposite to state that, ethical adherence ensures that resources reach the intended beneficiaries and by extension fosters community trust which is crucial for long-term program sustainability.

Comparing regional trends to national and global patterns, the findings are in tune with studies in Northern Nigeria and Muslim-majority countries, including Indonesia and Malaysia, where value-driven Islamic welfare programs have improved access to education, healthcare, and micro-finance (Farooq, 2018; Rahman, 2015). However, North-Central Nigeria presents a unique socio-cultural and economic factors, such as multi-ethnic communities and reliance on subsistence farming that influence program outcomes that highlighted the need for specific strategies in the area of the research study.

The study also identified persistent challenges like insufficient funding, weak institutional capacity, and limited community awareness, which are consistent with findings from prior Nigerian studies (Yusuf, 2017; Bello, 2019; Ahmad & Abdul-Rahman, 2018). In essence, addressing these challenges requires policy and institutional reforms like integrating value-driven ethical principles into poverty reduction mechanisms, strengthening *zakat* boards and *waqf* trusts, and promoting community engagement through awareness campaigns. Overall, this study bridges a critical gap in the literature by providing empirical evidence that is specific to North-Central Nigeria and demonstrated that, ethical Islamic welfare practices can effectively reduce poverty and by extension promote social justice, equity, and community development not only in the in North-Central Nigeria but also in other regions of Nigeria as well.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that Islamic social welfare programs in North-Central Nigeria effectively promote value-driven poverty alleviation, improving access to education, healthcare, and income-generating opportunities. The findings highlighted the ethical principles like transparency, accountability, fairness, and

community participation that are central to the success of *zakat*, *sadaqah*, and *waqf* interventions. While challenges such as insufficient funding, weak institutional capacity, and limited community awareness persist, the study confirms that these can be mitigated through strategic policy, institutional, and community-based interventions.

By providing empirical evidence specific to North-Central Nigeria, this study bridges a critical regional research gap, reinforcing the moral and social significance of value-driven Islamic welfare systems in poverty reduction and alleviation in Nigeria. The results also is in concord with prior scholarship emphasizing that ethically grounded social welfare programs that enhances both effectiveness and sustainability (Hassan & Haron, 2020; Ahmad & Abdul-Rahman, 2018; Yusuf, 2017; Bello, 2019).

Recommendations

- i. Strengthen institutional frameworks for coordination, monitoring, and accountability within zakat boards, *waqf* trusts, and Islamic NGOs.
- ii. Integrate value-driven Islamic welfare practices into regional poverty alleviation policies to ensure ethical and sustainable outcomes.
- iii. Promote ethical and value-driven practices through training, capacity-building, and workshops for program managers and community leaders.
- iv. Increase community awareness and participation to improve program uptake, transparency, and social accountability.
- v. Enhance funding and resource mobilization to expand program reach and sustainability, leveraging both public and private partnerships.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, S., & Abdul-Rahman, A. (2018). Ethical management of Islamic social welfare for poverty reduction. *Journal of Islamic Social Studies*, 15(2), 45–60.
- Al-Ghazālī, A. H. (2004). *Ihya' Ulum al-Din (Revival of the Religious Sciences)*. Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyyah.
- Bello, M. (2019). Zakat administration and poverty alleviation in Northern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Development Studies*, 11(1), 67–82.
- Farooq, A. (2018). Value-driven Islamic welfare programs in Egypt. *Journal of Islamic Economics*, 10(3), 35–50.

- Hassan, R., & Haron, R. (2020). Value-driven Islamic social welfare and community development. *International Journal of Islamic Economics*, 12(3), 55–73.
- Kamal, M. (2017). Waqf as a tool for sustainable social development. *Journal of Islamic Finance*, 6(1), 23–37.
- Kahf, M. (1999). *The Performance of the Institution of Zakah in Theory and Practice*. International Conference on Islamic Economics, Kuala Lumpur.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2020). *Poverty and socio-economic indicators in Nigeria*. Abuja: NBS.
- Rahman, S. (2015). Ethical principles in Islamic social welfare: Lessons from Southeast Asia. *Journal of Muslim Minority Affairs*, 35(2), 145–162.
- Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Yusuf, I. (2017). Islamic social welfare institutions and poverty reduction in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Policy*, 9(2), 101–118.